

Ref. number: 85

Date: 18/6/2023

Subject Approval Decision

To: Fatima Mustafa Ali, Athmar Dh. H. Al-Shohani

The Research Ethics Committee has received a request for ethical approval for the following research: Animal Study

Research No.	5
Approval No.	5
Project title	Preparation and evaluation of in situ eye gel with a dual triggered mechanism for the delivery of gatifloxacin and betamethasone sodium phosphate(study on rabbits for ocular irritation study)
Decision	Approved

According to the revision by the committee (please tick the proper decision):

☒	The research ethics committee gives approval to the research
☐	The research ethics committee gives approval to the research after completing the required corrections
☐	The research ethics committee refused the research

Prof. Dr. Inam Sameh Arif

Chairman of the Research Ethics Committee

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